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Bluetooth Controlled Vehicle

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Abstract: RF modules are used by many robots that are operated wirelessly. However, this idea uses an Android smartphone to drive a robotic arm. There are more control commands accessible than only RF modules. The user of an Android smartphone must install an application to do this. The user then has to activate the mobile device's Bluetooth. Bluetooth technology is the wireless communication method utilized to operate the robot. The Android mobile allows the user to send and receive many commands, such as move forward, move backward, move left, and move right. The robot is equipped with a Bluetooth receiver device that receives orders and sends them to the microcontroller circuit to operate the motors. To run the motors, the microcontroller then sends the signal to the motor driver's integrated circuits.

Keywords: Bluetooth, Vehicle

1. Introduction

To control the robot, this project combines the capabilities of a microcontroller and a mobile device. A radio frequency remote control system with a transmitter and a receiver is similar to how a mobile-controlled robot operates. As a result, two cell phones are needed for efficient signal transmission and receiving.

The user's phone, which connects to the robot's mobile phone through communication, controls the robot. When a button is touched during a phone call, the recipient will hear a tone known as a "Dual Tone Multiple Frequency" (DTMF) tone matching the button pressed. Via the receiver cell phone that is mounted on the board, the robot receives these tones. The microcontroller uses the DTMF decoder IC to handle the received tone.

The robot is driven in four directions—forward, reverse, right, and left—by the motor driver, which is in communication with the microcontroller based on the key pushed on the transmitter mobile. The robot is equipped with a wireless camera to enable it to perceive the physical elements of the surrounding environment.

2. SYSTEM DESIGN IMPLEMENTATION: -

Here, I've utilized a Bluetooth module to operate the robot, which has two BO motors spinning at about 300 RPM. An Android phone application controls the robot. The AT89S51 microcontroller, which is part of the 8051 family, is utilized to operate in the serial connection UART mode. Its communication speed is set to 9800bps to interface with the Bluetooth module. The Bluetooth module that is being utilized is an HC-05 in SMD packaging. It operates on 3.3 volts and can communicate serially with any device that is attached to it. Through the use of AT commands, the communication speed may be adjusted.

Since the BT module is an SPP-enabled profile, connecting to any module or phone is simple. The data can be delivered and received to the module using this profile. The microcontroller's RX pin is linked to the BT module. Depending on the logic provided to the logic pins, the L293D motor driver integrated circuit may run the motors in any direction that is needed. I utilized a prefabricated, small chassis instead of assembling the chassis myself. It has two decks: the upper serves as a battery stack, and the lower is where the BO motors are installed. The board is screw-mounted on top of the plate.

A robot controlled by an Android smartphone. Here's a straightforward method for controlling your robot or robot automobile with an Android smartphone device with the Bluetooth module HC-06 and 89c2051 microprocessor. A microcontroller is the system's main controlling component. DC motors and a Bluetooth module are interfaced with the microcontroller. The controller receives data as input from the Android smartphone using the Bluetooth module. The robot's DC motor is controlled appropriately by the controller. The Android phone may be used to control the robot's movement in all four directions in this project. Robot system LED indicators are used to indicate the robot's direction. An embedded "C" language program is loaded into the controller to do the operation. Android smartphone controller Bluetooth robot using microcontroller

A robot controlled by an Android smartphone. Here's a straightforward method for controlling your robot or robot automobile with an Android smartphone device with the Bluetooth module HC-06 and 89c2051 microprocessor. A microcontroller is the system's main controlling component. DC motors and a Bluetooth module are interfaced with the microcontroller. The controller receives data as input from the Android smartphone using the Bluetooth module. The robot's DC motor is controlled appropriately by the controller. The Android phone may be used to control the robot's movement in all four directions in this project. Robot system LED indicators are used to indicate the robot's direction. An embedded "C" language program is loaded into the controller to do the operation. Android smartphone controller Bluetooth robot using microcontroller

3. HARDWARE/COMPONENT: -

3.1.1 PCB Board Design: Developing a circuit that can connect with a Bluetooth module, like the HC-05 or HC-06, and control the vehicle's motors using a motor driver, such as the L298N, is necessary when designing a PCB board for Bluetooth-controlled cars. A high-level summary of the actions you may take is as follows:

3.1.2 Describe the Conditions: Decide the features you would like to have in a car that is operated by Bluetooth. This might involve steering, speed control, going forward and backward, and adding other features like lights or a horn.

- 3.1.3 **Choose Your Components:** Select the motors, motor driver, Bluetooth module, microcontroller (such as an Arduino), and any additional sensors or parts you require.
- 3.1.4 **Schematic Design:** Create your circuit's schematic diagram using an application such as Easy EDA or Ki CAD. To operate the vehicle's motors, this will include connecting the Bluetooth module to the microcontroller and the motor driver.¹²
- 3.1.5 **PCB Layout:** Use the same tool to convert your schematic into a PCB layout. By the design, arrange the components and route the traces to link them.
- 3.1.6 **Testing the Prototype:** Once the PCB has been manufactured, put the parts together and test the prototype to make sure everything functions as it should.
- 3.1.7 **Programming:** Create the code that will allow the microcontroller to manage motor control and Bluetooth connectivity. A program that can decode Bluetooth signals and translate them into motor motions will need to be written³⁴.

3.2 HC-05 BLUETOOTH MODULE:

A Bluetooth module called HC-05 is utilized for short-range wireless communication. This module communicates serially using a master and slave setup. A microcontroller is in communication with this module.

This module requires 3.6–6 V of electricity to operate. This module contains pins for GND, TXD, RXD, State, and VCC.

The 5V or 3.3 V Arduino pin is linked to the VCC pin. Wireless communication is used by TXD to send and receive data, and the State pin indicates whether a module is connected or not. The frequency of this gadget is between 2.4 and 2.5 GHz. The excellent precision, small size, good transmission, and band rate of this module make it useful for a wide range of applications, including wireless toys, wireless keyboards and mice, Alexa, and more. It has a range up to <100m which depends on Tx and Rx

HC-05 (Bluetooth Module)

3.3 **GRIPPY WHEELS:** There are several projects and materials available to help you if you're interested in building a Bluetooth-controlled car with gripping wheels. Here's a quick rundown of everything you could require:

Four gripping wheels were employed in our project. The use of gripping wheels is justified by their significant utility when turning. These wheels are linked to a TT gear motor by a wiser-to-wheel

3.4 **12V LITHIUM-ION BATTERY:** We have utilized the 12-volt lithium-ion battery mentioned above, which powers the motor. The fact that we can use the charger to recharge this battery is what matters most. This battery works incredibly well in the robotics industry. Additionally, with the rise in popularity of Tesla

electric vehicles, the need for this battery in the present day is growing daily. An essential component of an electric vehicle. This particular kind of battery is employed in Tesla Motors. It is connected to the Tesla Car 3000 by the use of a copper strip, which allows the battery to provide a significant quantity of electricity. You must use caution when utilizing this battery. Always keep positive and negative parts away from each other. If connected there is a chance of power loss.

4. WORKING

A robot controlled by an Android smartphone. Here's a straightforward method for controlling your robot or robot automobile with an Android smartphone device with the Bluetooth module HC-06 and 89c2051 microprocessor. A microcontroller is the system's main controlling component. DC motors and a Bluetooth module are interfaced with the microcontroller. The controller receives data as input from the Android smartphone using the Bluetooth module. The robot's DC motor is controlled appropriately by the controller. The Android phone may be used to control the robot's movement in all four directions in this project. Robot system LED indicators are used to indicate the robot's direction. An embedded "C" language program is loaded into the controller to do the operation.

Controller for Android smartphones The Bluetooth microcontroller robot is a block diagram of an 89s51 microcontroller-powered Bluetooth robot controller for Android smartphones 4. Instructions for Application 4.1 First, confirm that your phone and the HC-06 Bluetooth module are linked. For pairing, the default password is either "0000" or "1234". Examine the Bluetooth module's handbook. The module for Bluetooth: An HC-05 Bluetooth module with SPP capability is utilized. Qualities:

- 4.1 Bluetooth port for wireless serial communication.
- 4.2 The bottom board has a well-functioning power regulator and a free power adaptor. The user can link TX and RX to their control IO and connect 3.3 to 5VDC (generic 3.3 to 5V digital input-output of MCU or IO is fine, or general TTL IO).
- 4.3 Searching for and entering the "1234" passcode makes it simple to connect this module to the computer.
- 4.4 The adapter board has a white SMD LED that indicates the state of the Bluetooth connection. Step to establish a connection.
- 4.5 After connecting the wires and turning on the device, a white LED on the Bluetooth module board will blink.
- 4.6 Look for a Bluetooth device on the PC.
- 4.7 Discovered gadget named "HC-05" Initially, confirm that your mobile device and the HC-06 Bluetooth module are linked. For pairing, the default password is either "0000" or "1234". Examine the Bluetooth module's handbook. 4.2 To choose the associated Bluetooth module, click the "SELECT DEVICE" icon. 4.3 The Bluetooth module attached to the circuit receives the data "A" when the "up arrow" button is pressed. The robot or robot automobile advances when the microcontroller recognizes "A." 4.4 Pressing "DOWN ARROW" causes the Bluetooth module attached to the circuit to receive data "B." The robot or robot automobile travels in reverse when the microcontroller recognizes "B."
- 4.8 The Bluetooth module attached to the circuit receives the data "C" when the "LEFT ARROW" button is pressed. The robot or robot vehicle goes LEFT when the microcontroller exhibits a malfunction (C). 4.6 The Bluetooth module attached to the circuit receives the data "D" when the "RIGHT ARROW" button is pressed. The robot or robot vehicle turns RIGHT when there is a

microcontroller failure ("D"). 4.7 The Bluetooth module attached to the circuit receives the data "E" when the "STOP" button in the remote's center is pressed. The robot or robot vehicle stops when the microcontroller exhibits a flaw of type "E." 4.8 To unpair the linked Bluetooth module, select the "DISCONNECT" icon.

5. APPLICATIONS: -

- 5.1 It's a tool that can be used to spy.
- 5.2 Remote locations, including nuclear power plants, can be reached by mobile robots. It may be applied in high-radiation nuclear contexts, especially when a crisis or impending calamity is present.
- 5.3 Mines can be used to gather information using it.
- 5.4 It may be utilized to get rid of land mines that are buried at the border.

6. COST ESTIMATION: -

Sr.no	Name of components used	Quantity	Cost component (Rs.)
1	Battery 12V	1	700
2	HC-05 Bluetooth Module	1	350
3	Gear Motor	2	690
4	Connecting Wire	2m	100
5	PCB Board Design	1	3000
6	Switch	2	200
7	Motor Driver IC L298	1	400
			Total Cost = 5440

Table 1

7. ADVANTAGES:

- 7.1 **Wireless Data Transmission:** Wireless Device Pairing: For smooth communication, devices can form a wireless personal area network (WPAN).
 - 7.1.1 Bluetooth technology facilitates internet communication without the inconvenience of cables.
 - 7.1.2 Wireless synchronization allows for easy file transfers even in the absence of physical links.
 - 7.1.3 Bluetooth technology enables remote control of connected devices or appliances.
 - 7.1.4 Real-time location systems are employed to detect and locate items within a predetermined range.
 - 7.1.5 Personal Security: Guards against losing or stealing gadgets (like cell phones).
- 7.2 **Widespread Accessibility and Availability:** Bluetooth is extensively available:
 - 7.2.1 The majority of tablets, laptops, and smartphones have Bluetooth technology integrated into them.
 - 7.2.2 External adapters are a viable option for devices that do not have integrated components.
- 7.3 **Convenience and Usability:** o It's simple to pair devices that have integrated Bluetooth radios.
- 7.4 **Improving Access Control for Automotive:**
 - 7.4.1 The interaction between drivers and automobiles has changed as a result of Bluetooth technology.
 - 7.4.2 It acts as the replacement standard for car keyless

8. CONCLUSION: -

One of the most essential fundamental necessities for all living things is wireless control. Unfortunately, the technology is rarely completely utilized because of the enormous volume of data and transmission overheads. RF modules are used by many robots that are operated wirelessly. However, this concept uses readily accessible and inexpensive Android smartphones for robotic control. There are more control commands accessible than RF modules. The Android user must install an application on their device to do this. The user then has to activate the mobile device's Bluetooth. Bluetooth technology is the wireless communication method that is utilized to operate the robot.

With these orders, which are delivered from the Android smartphone, users may go forward, backward, left, and right, among other commands. The orders are received by the robot's Bluetooth receiver unit, which then transmits them to the microcontroller circuit to operate the motors. To run the motors, the microcontroller then sends the signal to the motor driver's integrated circuits. This article aims to implement smart living, especially a Bluetooth-enabled home lighting control system. Smartphones and robots are a great combination, particularly mobile robots.

With the increasing capability of phones and other mobile devices, robots with advanced functions like speech recognition may be built by utilizing these devices as building blocks. Android Bluetooth-enabled phones and Bluetooth module via HC-06 and communication among Bluetooth devices. It is determined that wireless and remote home control will become a reality with the progressive emergence of smart living.

9. FUTURE SCOPE: -

9.1 Bluetooth Enabled Keyless Entry

9.1.1 Smartphone as Key Fob: You can now use your smartphone as a car key fob thanks to Bluetooth technology. Your car knows you're the owner when you get close and open the doors. This feature improves security and convenience.

9.1.2 Customization: You may set your smartphone to unlock some doors (like your car's trunk or door) that you use frequently while locking others. Imagine having your hands full as you go to your car—this feature makes access easier.

9.1.3 Temporary Access: Do you have houseguests or need to lend your automobile to a friend? Without reprogramming locks or doors, you may temporarily provide access using your phone.

9.2 Beyond Keyless Entry:

9.2.1 The trend towards keyless access for cars is being driven by Bluetooth technology.

9.2.2 More wireless sensors are being added by automakers to enable a range of features, such as tire pressure monitoring and infotainment.

9.3 Digital Keys Revolution:

9.3.1 Digital keys are revolutionizing travel experiences and are quickly becoming a global trend.

9.3.2 An essential component of automobile access control is Bluetooth technology.

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